

A Ten Year Analysis of Intrauterine Fetal Deaths: An Age-Matched Case Control Study at a General Hospital in Sub-Saharan Africa

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Intrauterine Foetal Death (IUID) is one of the final pathways of adverse pregnancy outcome. It is a public health problem with increasing prevalence across diverse populations, especially in Sub-Saharan Africa.

Objective: This population-based study was aimed at determining the rate and risk factors for IUID in a secondary-level medical center in southern Nigeria

Methodology: This was a retrospective age-matched case control study carried out among 402 women who were on admission in the maternity ward of General Hospital Anua, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria between January 2006 and December 2017. They were selected using incidental non-probability sampling method from the hospital records. Data was analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences, version 23.

Results: Average maternal age was 24.26 years among the case and 23.56 among the control participants. The age group 18-29 had the most participants (49.8%). The risk of intrauterine foetal death was statistically significant when associated with adverse perinatal outcome [OR = 1.05 (95%CI: 1.01-1.09, p value < 0.001)]; **malpresentation** [OR = 0.16 (95%CI: 0.12-0.27, p value < 0.001)]; **previous caesarean section** [OR = 2.06 (95%CI: 1.31-2.61, p value < 0.001)]; **fetal macrosomia** [OR = 3.71 (95%CI: 3.06-4.91, p value < 0.001)]; **preclampsia** [OR = 1.34 (95%CI: 0.71-1.69, p value < 0.001)]; **ecclampsia** [OR = 2.96 (95%CI: 1.92-3.61, p value < 0.001)]; **oligohydramnios** [OR = 1.54 (95%CI: 1.12-1.94, p value < 0.001)]; **polyhydramnios** [OR = 1.49 (95%CI: 1.34-1.76, p value < 0.001)]; **placenta abruptio** [OR = 3.84 (95%CI: 1.71-5.61, p value < 0.001)]; **placenta praevia** [OR = 1.05 (95%CI: 1.62-2.19, p value < 0.001)]; **cord prolapse** [OR = 4.69 (95%CI: 2.17-6.19, p value < 0.001)]; **true knot** [OR = 3.16 (95%CI: 2.89-4.61, p value < 0.001)]; **and gestational diabetes** [OR = 1.01 (95%CI: 1.94-2.05, p value < 0.001)].

Conclusion: Intrauterine fetal demise is associated with several risk factors which can be maternal, fetal or placental. This underscores the need for adequate antenatal surveillance, birth preparedness and complication readiness to avert the misfortune.

Keyword: Intrauterine foetal death; stillbirth.

INTRODUCTION

Intrauterine Foetal Death (IUID) is better described as foetal death at a gestational age of 28 completed weeks or a crown-heel length of 35 cm or more and birth weight is at least 1000 g¹. It is also known as stillbirth. Annually, there are 287,000 maternal deaths² and over 3 million stillbirths, of which about a million die in the course of labour and about four million neonatal deaths, half of which happen on the day of birth³. Recent estimates suggest that stillbirth rates greater than 30 per 1000 births are common among the least developed countries, especially in Sub-Saharan Africa and Southeast Asia⁴. Stillbirths are underreported in developing countries, with about 97% of the cases occur in the region, and it accounts for 50% of worldwide perinatal deaths^{5,6}.

Stillbirth has been associated with some risk factors including maternal, foetal and placental. Documented maternal risk factors are as follows: un-booked status, illiteracy, age of 35 years and above in pregnancy, extremes of reproductive age groups, multiple pregnancies and prolonged labour. Foetal risk factors associated with stillbirth are malpresentation, decreased foetal movement, foetal distress, prematurity, small for gestational age, and neonatal infection⁷⁻¹⁵.

Other independent risk factors associated with stillbirth are: congenital malformations, true knot of cord, meconium stained amniotic fluid, oligo-hydramnios, poly-hydramnios, previous adverse perinatal outcome, placental abruption, advanced maternal age, and hypertensive disorders¹⁶. Jewish ethnicity, gestational diabetes, previous caesarean section, and recurrent abortions were negatively associated with intra-uterine foetal death[31]. Recent studies show that placental pathology plays a cardinal role in IUFD. Over 90% of the IUFD placentae examined in a recent study revealed some degree of placental vascular abnormalities, regardless of gestational age¹⁷.

This population-based study was aimed at determining the rate and risk factors for IUFD in a secondary-level medical center in southern Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

Study Location

General Hospital Anua is a secondary-level healthcare institution located in the state capital, Uyo. Akwa Ibom State is a state in Nigeria located on the southern part of the country lying between latitudes 4°32'N and 5°33'N, and longitudes 7°25'E and 8°25'E with a population of over 5 million people.

Study Design

This was a retrospective age-matched case control study using past clinical records in General Hospital Anua, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. Ethical approval was received from the Ethical Review Board of Akwa Ibom State Ministry of Health.

Sample

201 cases and 201 controls were selected after calculating for sample size¹⁸⁻²² using incidental non-probability sampling technique from the healthcare records of mothers on admission in the maternity ward of General Hospital Anua during the period January 2006 - November 2016. The cases were mothers who had fetal demise after 28 weeks gestational age and qualified as intrauterine fetal deaths. Controls were mothers who were admitted for normal labour and were discharged home with their babies alive. Exclusion criteria were: (1) intrapartum fetal death, (2) postpartum death, (3) multiple gestations, and (4) termination of pregnancies.

Measure

Demographic and clinical characteristics regarding ethnicity, maternal age, gestational age, and birth number were recorded. Risk factors such as maternal body mass index (BMI) at delivery, habitual smoking, suspected intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR), multiparity, oligohydramnios (amniotic fluid index fluid), polyhydramnios (amniotic fluid index of 24 cm), cord abnormalities (true knot, nuchal cord, cord prolapse), placental abruption, and meconium-stained amniotic fluid were examined. Other clinical features such as previous adverse pregnancy outcome, diabetes mellitus, recurrent abortions, and hypertensive disorders (chronic hypertension, preeclampsia and eclampsia) were also registered. Gestational age was determined by the estimated date of delivery, while daily cigarette consumption during pregnancy was defined as the habit of smoking.

Analysis

The questionnaires were carefully examined for correctness and completeness, coded and analysed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23 for Windows. Quantitative data generated from the study was presented in form of tables and analysed as descriptive frequencies and percentages. Statistical significance was tested using the w2 or Fisher's exact test for differences in categorical variables. For continuous variables, student T-test or one-way ANOVA was applied. A backwards multivariable logistic regression model was constructed to find independent factors associated with IUFD and to control for confounders. Odds ratios (OR) and 95% confidence Intervals (CI) were also calculated. P-value of less than 0.05 was accepted to be statistically significant.

RESULTS

The average maternal age was 24.26 years among the case and 23.56 among the control participants. The age group 18-29 had the most participants (49.8%) and this value was the same for both case and control because the study was an age-matched study. Other characteristics are as shown in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics

Variable	IUFD (n = 201)	No IUFD (n = 201)	P value
Maternal age (years)	24.26 +/- 6.37	23.56 +/- 2.84	0.813
Maternal age (years)			
<18	14(7.0)	14(7.0)	0.000
18-29	100(49.8)	100(49.8)	
30-39	85(42.3)	85(42.3)	
>40	2(0.9)	2(0.9)	
Gestational age at delivery	36 +/- 7.81	38 +/- 6.14	0.012
Gestational age			
28-21 weeks	43(21.4)	41(20.4)	0.362
32-36weeks	66(32.8)	62(30.8)	
>37 weeks	92(45.8)	98(48.8)	
Parity	1.07 +/- 0.84	1.04 +/- 0.82	<0.01
BMI	26.4 +/- 2.61	27.2 +/- 4.17	<0.001
Caesarean section	23(11.4)	74(36.8)	<0.001
Smoking	2(0.99)	0(0)	0.156

Table 2 shows the maternal and pregnancy risk factors for IUFD that were explored in the study. All were significant except chronic hypertension and nuchal cord. They are as shown below.

Table 2: Maternal and Pregnancy-Related Risk Factors

Variable	IUFD	No IUFD	OR	95% CI	P value
Adverse perinatal outcome	26(12.9)	8(4.0)	1.05	1.01-1.09	<0.001
Recurrent abortions	29(14.4)	5(2.5)	1.31	0.72-2.59	0.618
Malpresentation	27(13.4)	16(7.9)	0.16	0.12-0.27	<0.001
Previous C/S	61(30.3)	43(21.4)	2.06	1.31-2.61	<0.001
Fetal macrosomia	6(2.9)	16(8.0)	3.71	3.06-4.91	<0.001
Hypertensive disorders					
Chronic hypertension	5(2.5)	14(7.0)	1.12	0.51-1.50	0.478
Preclampsia	37(18.4)	44(21.9)	1.34	0.71-1.69	<0.001
Ecclampsia	21(10.4)	3(1.5)	2.96	1.92-3.61	<0.001
Oligohydramnios	23(11.4)	2(0.9)	1.54	1.12-1.94	<0.001
Polyhydramnios	19(9.5)	3(1.5)	1.49	1.34-1.76	<0.001
Placenta abruption	35(17.4)	2(0.9)	3.84	1.71-5.61	<0.001
Placenta Praevia	34(16.9)	20(10.0)	1.05	1.62-2.19	<0.001
Cord Prolapse	7(3.5)	2(0.9)	4.69	2.17-6.19	<0.001
Nuchal cord	42(20.9)	33(16.4)	1.14	0.78-1.29	0.261
True knot	9(4.5)	16(8.0)	3.16	2.89-4.61	<0.001
Gestational Diabetes	4(1.9)	2(0.9)	1.01	1.94-2.05	<0.001

DISCUSSION

This is a retrospective case control study done in General Hospital Anua to assess the risk factors for intrauterine fetal deaths (IUFD) among women admitted into the maternity ward. The maternal age at delivery, gestational age at delivery, parity, body mass index (BMI), and caesarean section as mode of delivery were all significant demographic and clinical characteristics. Some maternal demographic factors were associated with an increased risk of intrauterine fetal death. In this study, maternal age was seen to be statistically significant when associated with the presence or absence of IUFD. Advanced maternal age has been shown to have an increased risk for IUFD in a number of studies^{24, 25, 26}. A study reported that early and later aged pregnancies are shown to have significantly higher risk of fetal loss with respect to advanced maternal age²⁷. A study of pregnancy outcomes in women aged 35 to 40 years found a 1.4-fold increase in stillbirth compared to younger women; the increase was 2.4-fold higher in women over age 40²⁸. The same authors noted no increased risk of fetal mortality in women less than 18 years of age²⁹, although others have found an association³⁰. In another study, older women had a significantly higher risk for unexplained fetal death³¹.

The association between body mass index and the presence or absence of IUFD was seen to be statistically significant in this study. The relationship of pre-pregnancy body-mass-index (BMI) to late fetal death was examined in a population-based cohort of 167,750 Swedish women³². Among nulliparous women, the odds ratios for late fetal death increased threefold among women with BMI values 25 to 29.9 and fourfold in women with BMI >30 as compared to lean women. The mechanism(s) for this association is not known.

Smoking was not found to be statistically significant when associated with IUFD in this study. Smoking is associated with several adverse pregnancy outcomes, including stillbirth, abruption, and fetal growth restriction³³⁻³⁸. Furthermore, smoking carried into the 3rd trimester is found to have a more significant influence on the risk of stillbirth than smoking during the 2nd trimester³⁹.

This study also reported an increased risk for IUFD among women with an adverse perinatal outcome. A previous study by Weintraub et al.⁴⁰ documented that previous adverse perinatal outcome was an independent risk factor for consequent IUFD. Recurrent abortion was seen to be a protective risk factor against IUFD. This may be because of increased and deliberate antenatal surveillance in women with recurrent abortions.

This study assessed umbilical cord pathologies as predictors of risk for IUFD. Umbilical cord pathology includes prolapse, true knots, stricture, and strangulation of the fetus. While true knots and prolapsed was significantly associated with IUFD, nuchal cord was not. Previous studies have reported that the risk for IUFD in cases of umbilical cord pathologies increases as the pregnancy continues and may lead to fetal demise in late pregnancy with values ranging from 19% to 56.6% of all stillbirths and a rate of 5.7 per 1000 deliveries^{41,42}. In one study, the incidence of umbilical cord knots was 1 percent⁴³. The fetal mortality rate was higher in cords with a knot compared to knot-free cords, 2.7 versus 0.5 percent, respectively⁴³.

It has however been reported that the presence of a nuchal cord antepartum is often transient⁴⁴; nevertheless, nuchal cords are associated with increased risk to the foetus⁴⁵. One series found that single nuchal cords were present in one quarter of deliveries and multiple nuchal cords were present in 3.7 percent⁴⁶. An increase in blood flow resistance has been noted with even a single nuchal coil, oxygen saturation of umbilical cord blood can be altered, and a persistent nuchal cord can be associated with reduction in the middle cerebral artery S/D ratio (suggesting redistribution of blood flow to the brain)^{44,46}.

Consequently, nuchal cords can be associated with fetal distress in labor, passage of meconium, growth restriction, and lower APGAR scores⁴⁷. In spite of this however, that the mere presence of one or multiple coils is rarely associated with fetal mortality^{43,45}. An important distinction should be made between the types of coiling to assess the degree of risk. A type A encirclement can undo itself, as the placental insertion end crosses over the umbilical insertion end. By comparison, in a type B coil the placental end crosses under the umbilical end, and it therefore becomes locked⁴⁸. It is opined that type B encirclements, therefore, are the ones that increase the risk of fetal mortality⁴⁹. Nuchal cord has been reported to be a relatively common condition, which has been shown not to be associated with adverse perinatal outcome⁵⁰.

In this study, preeclampsia and eclampsia were significantly associated with IUFD. A previous study reported that about 5.6-9.4% of pregnancies complicated by preeclampsia end in intrauterine fetal demise^{51,52}. A meta-analysis of five studies

⁵³⁻⁵⁷ confirmed that pre-existing hypertension remains an important risk factor for stillbirth, and was associated with a rise in the odds of stillbirth of around 2.6 times.

Gestational diabetes mellitus was found to be significantly associated with IUFD. Previous studies have reported that there is a 2- to 5-fold risk of stillbirth for overt diabetes mellitus⁵⁸⁻⁶⁰. Risks of complication such as preeclampsia and stillbirth are also increased in type 1 diabetic pregnancy as compared to pregnancy in the general population, giving an odds ratio of 4.47 and 3.34, respectively⁶¹. Obesity increases the risk of type 2 and pregnancy-related diabetes, which further increases the risk of adverse outcomes for mothers and babies⁶².

Placenta abruption was associated with an increased risk for IUFD. Placental abruption complicates 1-3.75% of pregnancies^{63,64} and accounts for 9-15.2% of total stillbirths. The stillbirth rate from placental abruption is about 0.5/1000 birth^{63,65}. Although the majority of placental abruption cases are of unknown cause, there are several predisposing factors to it, including traumatic and non-traumatic factors. Individual results of two studies showed^{66,67} a strong association between placental abruption and stillbirth.

CONCLUSION

Intrauterine fetal demise is associated with several risk factors which can be maternal, fetal or placental. This underscores the need for adequate antenatal surveillance, birth preparedness and complication readiness to avert the misfortune.

REFERENCES

1. Lawn J, Shibuya K, Stein C. No cry at birth: Global estimates of intra partum stillbirths and intra partum-related neonatal deaths. *Bulletin of the World Health Organization*, 2005; 83 suppl 2: 409-417. Available from: URL: <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2626256/>
2. WHO, UNICEF, UNFPA and The World Bank estimates. Trends in maternal mortality: 1990 to 2008. Geneva, World Health Organization, 2010. Available from: URL: <http://www.who.int/reproductivehealth/publications/monitoring/9789241500265/en/>
3. Lawn JE, Kerber K, Enweronu-Laryea C, Masee Bateman O. Newborn survival in low resource settings--are we delivering? *BJOG* 2009; 116 Suppl 1: 49-59 [PMID: 19740173 DOI: 10.1111/j.1471-0528.2009.02328.x
4. Stanton C, Lawn JE, Rahman H, Wilczynska-Ketende K, Hill K (2006) Review Stillbirth rates: delivering estimates in 190 countries. *Lancet* 367: 1487-1494.
5. McClure EM, Wright LL, Goldenberg RL, Goudar SS, Parida SN, Jehan I, et al. The global network: a prospective study of stillbirths in developing countries. *Am J Obstet Gynecol* 2007;197(247):e1e5.
6. Lawn JE, Cousens S, Bhutta ZA, Darmstadt GL, Martines J, Paul V, et al. Why are 4 million newborn babies dying each year? *Lancet* 2004;364:399e401.
7. Fretts, R. (2010). Stillbirth epidemiology, Risk factors, and Opportunities for stillbirth prevention. *Clinical Obstetric Gynecology*, 53(3): 588-96.
8. Association between Stillbirth and Risk factors known at Pregnancy confirmation. *Journal of the American Medical Association*, 306(22): 2469-79.
9. ACOG Practice bulletin No 102. (2009). Management of Stillbirth. *Obstetric and Gynecology*, 113(3): 748-61.
10. Smith, G. C. (2010). Predicting Antepartum Stillbirth. *Clinical Obstetric and Gynecology*, 53(3): 597-606.
11. Salihu, H. M. (2011). Maternal Obesity and Stillbirth. *Seminars in Perinatology*, 35(6): 340-4.
12. Bukowski, R. (2010). Stillbirth and Fetal Growth Restriction. *Clinical Obstetric and Gynecology*, 53(3): 673-80.
13. Reddy, U. M., Laughon, S. K., Sun, L., Troendle, J., Willinger, M., & Zhang, J. (2010). Prepregnancy Risk factors for Antepartum Stillbirth in the United States. *Obstetrics Gynecology*, 116(5): 1119-26.
14. Ananth, C. V., & Basso, O. (2010). Impact of Pregnancy-Induced Hypertension on Stillbirth and Neonatal Mortality. *Epidemiology*, 21(1): 118-23.
15. Venners, S. A., Wang, X., Chen, C., Wang, L., Chen, D., Guang, W., Xu, X. (2004). Paternal Smoking and Pregnancy Loss: A Prospective Study

- Using a Biomarker of Pregnancy. *American Journal of Epidemiology*, 159 (10): 993-1001.
16. Olamijulo JA, Olaleye O. Perinatal mortality in Lagos University Teaching Hospital: a five year review. *Nig Q J Hosp Med* 2011; 21: 255-261 [PMID: 23175887]
 17. Ohana O, Holcberg G, Sergienko R, Sheiner E. Risk factors for intrauterine fetal death (1988-2009). *J Matern Fetal Neonatal Med* 2011; 24: 1079-1083 [PMID: 21314292 DOI: 10.3109/14767058.2010.545918]
 18. Chow SC, Shao J, Wang H. Sample Size Calculations in Clinical Research. New York: Marcel Dekker; 2003.
 19. D'Agostino RB, Chase W, Belanger A. The Appropriateness of Some Common Procedures for Testing the Equality of Two Independent Binomial Populations. *Am Stat*. 1988;42(3):198-202.
 20. Fleiss JL, Levin B, Paik MC. Statistical Methods for Rates and Proportions. 3rd ed. New York: John Wiley & Sons; 2003.
 21. Lachin JM. Biostatistical Methods. New York: John Wiley & Sons; 2000.
 22. Machin D, Campbell M, Fayers P, Pinol A. Sample Size Tables for Clinical Studies. 2nd ed. Malden: Blackwell Science; 1997.
 23. Copper, RL, Goldenberg, RL, DuBard, MB, Davis, RO. Risk factors for fetal death in white, black, and Hispanic women. Collaborative Group on Preterm Birth Prevention. *Obstet Gynecol* 1994; 84:490.
 24. Efkarpidis S, Alexopoulos E, Kean L, Liu D, Fay T. Case-control study of factors associated with intrauterine fetal deaths. *MedGenMed* 2004;6:53.
 25. Bahtiyar MO, Funai EF, Rosenberg V, Norwitz E, Lipkind H, Buhimschi C, et al. Stillbirth at term in women of advanced maternal age in the United States: when could the antenatal testing be initiated? *Am J Perinatol* 2008;25:301e4.
 26. Hsieh TT, Liou JD, Hsu JJ, Lo LM, Chen SF, Hung TH. Advanced maternal age and adverse perinatal outcomes in an Asian Population. *Eur J Obstet Gynecol Reprod Biol* 2010;148:21e6.
 27. MacDorman, M. F., Kirmeyer, S. E., & Wilson, E. C. Fetal and Perinatal Mortality, United States, 2006. *National Vital Statistics Reports*. 2012: Volume 60 Number 8.
 28. Jolly, M, Sebire, N, Harris, J, et al. The risks associated with pregnancy in women aged 35 years or older. *Hum Reprod* 2000; 15:2433.
 29. Jolly, MC, Sebire, N, Harris, J, et al. Obstetric risks of pregnancy in women less than 18 years old [In Process Citation]. *Obstet Gynecol* 2000; 96:962.
 30. Petitti, DB. The epidemiology of fetal death. *Clin Obstet Gynecol* 1987; 30:253.
 31. Fretts, RC, Usher, RH. Causes of fetal death in women of advanced maternal age. *Obstet Gynecol* 1997; 89:40.
 32. Cnattingius, S, Bergstrom, R, Lipworth, L, Kramer, MS. Prepregnancy weight and the risk of adverse pregnancy outcomes. *N Engl J Med* 1998; 338:147
 33. Data from the National Center for Health Statistics, 1990. Available at <http://www.cdc.gov/nchs/about/major/fetaldth/abfetal.htm#Data%20Highlights>.
 34. Ventura, SJ. Births to unmarried mothers: United States, 1980- 92. *Vital Health Stat* 21; 1995.
 35. Tuthill, DP, Stewart, JH, Coles, EC, et al. Maternal cigarette smoking and pregnancy outcome. *Paediatr Perinat Epidemiol* 1999;13:245.
 36. Flenady V, Middleton P, Smith GC, Duke W, Erwich JJ, Khong TY, et al. Stillbirths: the way forward in high-income countries. *Lancet* 2011;377:1703-17.
 37. Flenady V, Koopmans L, Middleton P, Froen JF, Smith GC, Gibbons K, et al. Major risk factors for stillbirth in high-income countries: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Lancet* 2011;377:1331-40.
 38. Crane JM, Keough M, Murphy P, Burrage L, Hutchens D. Effects of environmental tobacco smoke on perinatal outcomes: a retrospective cohort study. *BJOG* 2011;118:865-71.
 39. Liu LC, Huang HB, Yu MH, Su HY. Analysis of intrauterine fetal demised hospital-based study in Taiwan over a decade. *Taiwan J Obstet Gynecol* 2013;52:546-50.
 40. Weintraub AY, Rozen A, Sheiner E, Levy A, Press F, Wiznitzer A. Perinatal mortality: a sporadic event or a recurrent catastrophe? *Arch Gynecol Obstet* 2009;279:299-303.
 41. Shaaban LA, Al-Saleh RA, Alwafi BM, Al-Raddadi RM. Associated risk factors with ante-partum intrauterine fetal death. *Saudi Med J* 2006;27:76-9.
 42. Peng HQ, Levitin-Smith M, Rochelson B, Kahn E. Umbilical cord stricture and overcoiling are common causes of fetal demise. *Pediatr Dev Pathol* 2006;9: 14-9.
 43. Sornes, T. Umbilical cord knots. *Acta Obstet Gynecol Scand* 2000;79:157.
 44. Clapp JF, 3rd, Stepanchak, W, Hashimoto, K, et al. The natural history of antenatal nuchal cords. *Am J Obstet Gynecol* 2003; 189:488.
 45. Larson, JD, Rayburn, WF, Crosby, S, Thurnau, GR. Multiple nuchal cord entanglements and intrapartum complications. *Am J Obstet Gynecol* 1995; 173:1228.
 46. Carey, JC, Rayburn, WF. Nuchal cord encirclements and risk of stillbirth. *Int J Gynaecol Obstet* 2000; 69:173.

47. Spellacy, WN, Gravem, H, Fisch, RO. The umbilical cord complications of true knots, nuchal coils, and cords around the body. *Am J Obstet Gynecol* 1966; **94**:1136.
48. Larson, JD, Rayburn, WF, Harlan, VL. Nuchal cord entanglements and gestational age. *Am J Perinatol* 1997; **14**:555.
49. Collins, JH. Nuchal cord type A and type B. *Am J Obstet Gynecol* 1997; **177**:94.
50. Sheiner E, Abramowicz JS, Levy A, Silberstein T, Mazor M, Herskovitz R. Nuchal cord is not associated with adverse perinatal outcome. *Arch Gynecol Obstet*. 2006;**274**:81–83.
51. Wood S, Chen S, Ross S, Sauve R. The risk of unexplained antepartum stillbirth in second pregnancies following caesarean section in the first pregnancy. *BJOG* 2008; **11**: 726–31.
52. Alexander GR, Slay Wingate M, Salihu H, Kirby RS. Fetal and neonatal mortality risks of multiple births. *Obstet Gynecol Clin North Am* 2005; **32**: 1–16, vii
53. Flenady V. Causes and risk factors of stillbirths in Australia. Perinatal Society of Australia and New Zealand congress 2008; Gold Coast. *Paediatr Child Health* 2008; **2**–10.
54. Froen JF, Gardosi JO, Thurmann A, Francis A, Stray-Pedersen B. Restricted fetal growth in sudden intrauterine unexplained death. *Acta Obstet Gynecol Scand* 2004; **83**: 801–07.
55. Allen VM, Joseph K, Murphy KE, Magee LA, Ohlsson A. The effect of hypertensive disorders in pregnancy on small for gestational age and stillbirth: a population based study. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth* 2004; **4**: 17.
56. Ananth CV, Savitz DA, Bowes WA Jr. Hypertensive disorders of pregnancy and stillbirth in North Carolina, 1988 to 1991. *Acta Obstet Gynecol Scand* 1995; **74**: 788–93.
57. Zetterstrom K, Lindeberg SN, Haglund B, Hanson U. The association of maternal chronic hypertension with perinatal death in male and female offspring: a record linkage study of 866,188 women. *BJOG* 2008; **115**: 1436–42.
58. Astolfi P, De Pasquale A, Zonta L. Late childbearing and its impact on adverse pregnancy outcome: stillbirth, preterm delivery and low birth weight. *Rev Epidemiol Sante Publique* 2005; **53**: 2S97–105.
59. Cnattingius S, Haglund B, Kramer MS. Differences in late fetal death rates in association with determinants of small for gestational age fetuses: population based cohort study. *BMJ* 1998; **316**: 1483–87.
60. Craig ED, Mantell CD, Ekeroma AJ, Stewart AW, Mitchell EA. Ethnicity and birth outcome: New Zealand trends 1980-2001. Part 1. Introduction, methods, results and overview. *Aust N Z J Obstet Gynaecol* 2004; **44**: 530–36
61. Salihu HM, Wilson RE, Alio AP, Kirby RS. Advanced maternal age and risk of antepartum and intrapartum stillbirth. *J Obstet Gynaecol Res* 2008; **34**: 843–50.
62. Rasmussen KM, Yaktine AL, eds. Committee to Reexamine IOM Pregnancy Weight Guidelines, Food and Nutrition Board, Board on Children, Youth and Families, Institute of Medicine, National Research Council. Weight gain during pregnancy: reexamining the guidelines. Washington, DC: National Academies Press, 2009.
63. Flegal KM, Graubard BI, Williamson DF. Methods of calculating deaths attributable to obesity. *Am J Epidemiol* 2004; **160**: 331–38.
64. McDonald SD, Vermeulen MJ, Ray JG. Risk of fetal death associated with maternal drug dependence and placental abruption: a population-based study. *J Obstet Gynaecol Can* 2007; **29**: 556–59.
65. Salihu HM, Bekan B, Aliyu MH, Rouse DJ, Kirby RS, Alexander GR. Perinatal mortality associated with abruption placenta in singletons and multiples. *Am J Obstet Gynecol* 2005; **193**: 198–203.
66. Hogberg L, Cnattingius S. The influence of maternal smoking habits on the risk of subsequent stillbirth: is there a causal relation? *BJOG* 2007; **114**: 699–704.
67. Aliyu MH, Salihu HM, Keith LG, Ehiri JE, Islam MA, Jolly PE. Extreme parity and the risk of stillbirth. *Obstet Gynecol* 2005; **106**: 446–53.